

1 **FRONT MATTER**

2 **Title:** Light-activated molecular machines are new mode-of-action, fast-acting broad-
3 spectrum antibacterials that target the membrane

4 **Short title:** New visible light activated molecular machines kill bacteria without
5 resistance

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28

Abstract

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The increasing occurrence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and the dwindling antibiotic research and development pipeline have created a pressing global health crisis. Here we report the discovery of a new antibacterial therapy that uses visible (405 nm) light-activated synthetic molecular machines (MM) to kill Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, in minutes, vastly outpacing conventional antibiotics. MM also rapidly eliminate persister cells and established bacterial biofilms. The antibacterial mode of action of MM involves physical disruption of the membrane. Additionally, by permeabilizing the membrane, MM at sublethal doses potentiate the action of conventional antibiotics. Importantly, repeated exposure to antibacterial MM is not accompanied by resistance development. Finally, therapeutic doses of MM mitigate mortality associated with bacterial infection in an *in vivo* model of burn wound infection. Visible light-activated MM represent a new antibacterial mode of action by mechanical disruption at the molecular scale, not existent in nature and to which resistance development is unlikely.

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46 **Teaser**

47 Visible light-activated molecular machines (MM) represent a new broad-spectrum
48 antibacterial therapy that kills bacteria by mechanical action within minutes without
49 detectable resistance.

50

51 MAIN TEXT

52 Introduction

53 Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents one of the greatest challenges facing
54 humankind (1). AMR is currently responsible for 700,000 deaths per year (2). By 2050, 10
55 million lives per year worldwide will be at risk from drug-resistant infections (3).

56 While long-established classes of conventional antibiotics are becoming
57 increasingly ineffective against a growing number of drug-resistant pathogens, the
58 development of new antimicrobial agents has nearly stagnated. No new class of antibiotics
59 against Gram-negative bacteria has been approved since the late 1980s (4) and only 1 in 4
60 antibiotics under clinical development is a novel drug class or acts *via* a new mechanism of
61 action (5). This makes most antibiotics under development susceptible to the same
62 resistance mechanisms of previously developed molecules. There is, therefore, an urgent
63 global need to develop safe and effective new antimicrobials that limit the rise of bacterial
64 resistance while preserving the viability of existing antibiotics.

65 Over the last decade, antimicrobial nanomaterials that are novel to bacteria and thus
66 are not *a priori* within their natural defensive arsenal have gained increasing attention as an
67 emerging “outside the box” approach against antibiotic-resistant bacteria (6, 7). Stimuli-
68 activated, “smart” nanomaterials are particularly appealing antimicrobials due to their
69 ability to precisely control their activities in time and/or in space, mitigating detrimental
70 side effects to human cells (8).

71 Synthetic molecular motors, or molecular machines (MM), are molecular structures
72 that can rotate unidirectionally in a controlled manner in response to stimuli, resulting in a
73 mechanical action (9). Among the stimuli that can activate MM, light is particularly
74 appealing due to its non-chemical, non-invasive nature, and ease of control. Synthetic MM
75 consist of a stator and a light-activated rotor (**Fig. 1A**). Following irradiation, the molecule
76 undergoes successive unidirectional rotation resulting in a drilling-like rapid (≈ 3 MHz)
77 motion (**Fig. 1B**) that can propel it through a lipid bilayer (**Fig. 1C**) (10). MM show great
78 promise in a multitude of applications, from drug delivery to chemo- and antimicrobial
79 therapy (9, 11, 12). However, reliance on UV-radiation for activation limits the clinical
80 utility of previously developed MM due to the detrimental effects of such wavelengths to
81 mammalian cells (13).

82 Here we report six visible light (405 nm) activated MM that kill Gram-negative and
83 Gram-positive bacteria, including methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), in as little as 2
84 min of light activation without detectable resistance. This new antimicrobial therapy is
85 effective not only against exponentially growing planktonic cells but also resistant
86 phenotypes, such as biofilms and persister cells. Using electron microscopy, RNAseq, and
87 spectrophoto- and spectrofluorimetric methods, the mode of action of MM was found to
88 involve mechanical disruption of the membrane, leakage of intracellular material, and loss
89 of membrane potential. Additionally, sublethal treatment with MM potentiated the action of
90 conventional antibiotics as a result of MM-induced membrane permeabilization and
91 enhanced antibiotic access to intracellular targets. Finally, at therapeutic levels, MM
92 mitigated mortality associated with infection by different bacterial strains (*A. baumannii*
93 and *S. aureus*) in a burn wound infection model.

94 MM represent a new stimuli-activated antibacterial therapy whose mechanism is
95 based on mechanical action at the molecular scale. This unique mechanism of action is
96 unlike that of any other antibacterial compound and the development of resistance to MM
97 is unlikely.

98 Results

99 *MM are fast-acting broad-spectrum antibacterials*

100 A library of 19 different visible light-activated (405 nm) MM displaying fast rotation
101 rates (≈ 3 MHz) was synthesized (**Table S1**). Visible light activation (**Fig. S1**) was achieved
102 by introducing an amine or alkoxy electron-donating substituent into the conjugated core of
103 the MM. The molecules were further modified with different amines in either the stator or
104 the rotor portion of the molecule to promote the association between the protonated amines
105 of the MM and the negatively charged bacterial membrane.

106 This MM library was originally screened for antibacterial activity in *Escherichia*
107 *coli* BW25113 (**Fig. 1D**). *E. coli* cell suspensions were incubated with a range of
108 concentrations (0.3125 - 40 μM) of the different MM (8 mM stock in DMSO) and then
109 irradiated for 5 min with 405 nm light at 146 mW cm^{-2} (43.8 J cm^{-2}). DMSO-only controls
110 were included in every experiment to exclude possible effects of the vehicle. Irradiated cell
111 suspensions were collected and inoculated into cation-adjusted Mueller-Hinton broth
112 (MHB). Following overnight incubation (37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), samples were inspected for growth. The
113 minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of light-activated MM was defined as the
114 concentration of MM resulting in no visible bacterial growth following irradiation with 43.8
115 J cm^{-2} of 405 nm light (**Fig. S2**).

116 The MIC of the different MM in *E. coli* is shown in **Fig. 1E**. Six fast-rotating MM
117 (MM 1 through MM 6) (**Fig. 1F**) displaying MIC values within the range of concentrations
118 tested were identified. MM 4, characterized by the presence of a triphenylphosphonium
119 (TPP⁺) group, displayed the lowest MIC in *E. coli* (0.625 μM), closely followed by MM 1
120 (1.25 μM). MM 2, characterized by the presence of a tertiary amine on the side chain of the
121 rotor portion of the molecule, displayed the highest MIC (32 μM). Slow rotating MM
122 controls ($\approx 10^{-3}$ Hz) (**Table S1**) did not exhibit antibacterial activity (**Fig. S3**), denoting the
123 importance of fast rotation rates for the antibacterial properties of MM. However,
124 substantial differences in rotation rates of the different antibacterial MM were not detected
125 (**Fig. S4**), suggesting that small variations in the rotation rate of fast MM cannot explain
126 differences in their antibacterial activity.

127 Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations revealed substantial differences in the
128 distributions of angles between the MM axle and the plane of the membrane of the most
129 potent (MM 1) and the least potent (MM 2) antibacterial MM (**Fig. S5**). In the case of MM
130 1, the axle of the molecule is close to parallel to the membrane (average angle of $\approx 15^{\circ}$),
131 while for MM 2 the axle is more perpendicular to the membrane (average angle of $\approx 60^{\circ}$)
132 (**Fig. S5A**). These observations indicate that MM 1 and MM 2 adopt distinct equilibrium
133 configurations when bound to the lipid bilayer membrane (**Fig. 1G**), as a result of the
134 different placement of the positively charged tertiary amine group in MM 1 and MM 2.
135 Equilibrium simulations also revealed that the axle of MM 1 can penetrate about 2 \AA deeper
136 into the membrane than that of MM 2, denoted by the slight left shift of the histogram of
137 the distributions of distances between geometric centers of axles of the MM and membrane

center of MM 1 relatively to MM 2 (Fig. S5B). This is also supported by the finding that the potential of mean force (PMF) curve for MM 1 is lower and slightly to the left of the PMF curve of MM 2 (Fig. S6), suggesting that it is more favorable for MM 1 to be located deeper inside the membrane. These differences in orientation and positioning of the two molecules within the membrane, and subsequent differences in the way they rotate following light activation, might influence the extent of the membrane deformation they exert and thus account for their distinct antibacterial activities.

The bacteriostatic potential of the identified MM (Fig. 1F) was further investigated in additional Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacterial strains (Table S2, Table S3). Killing by light-activated MM varied in a concentration- and light-intensity-dependent manner, with enhanced MM concentration and light intensity resulting in higher MM-induced killing (Fig. S7). Some toxicity of the MM itself (in the absence of light) was detected, particularly for the TPP⁺ containing MM 4 (Fig. S7), which was, therefore, excluded in subsequent “mode-of-action” experiments. Among the strains tested, *S. aureus* was particularly susceptible to killing by high MM concentrations even in the absence of light. *S. aureus* also exhibited substantial sensitivity to 405 nm light alone (Fig. S7). Light dose-dependent reduction of bacterial numbers by different concentrations of the most potent MM (MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6) revealed that complete eradication of *A. baumannii* and *E. coli* required at least 40 J cm⁻² of 405 nm light in samples treated with the highest concentration of MM tested (5 μM). Complete eradication of *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* could be achieved with 16 J cm⁻² of 405 nm light and 0.625 to 5 μM of MM (Fig. S8).

The bactericidal properties of MM (2x MIC) were further examined at a fixed light intensity of 146 mW cm⁻² (Table S4, Fig. 2A). In *A. baumannii*, treatment with different MM reduced cell number to the limit of detection in 3 min (MM 4) to 10 min (MM 3). In *E. coli*, bacterial numbers were reduced to the limit of detection in 4 min (MM 4, MM 5, MM 6) to 10 min (MM 2) of irradiation in the presence of 2x MIC of each MM. For *P. aeruginosa*, MM-induced reduction of cell numbers to the limit of detection was achieved in 3 min (MM 1, MM 4) to 10 min (MM 3, MM 6). Complete elimination of *S. aureus* was achieved in 2 min (MM 4) to 4 min (MM 2, MM 3) of irradiation.

The antibacterial spectrum of action of the most efficient MM (MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6) was assessed in additional strains, including methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) (Fig. 2B). The MIC of MM 1 ranged from 0.078 μM in *B. megaterium* and *S. epidermidis* to 10 μM in *B. cepacia* and *B. cereus*. The MIC of MM 5 ranged from 0.078 μM in *B. megaterium*, *S. aureus*, and *S. epidermidis* to 20 μM in *B. cepacia* and *E. cloacae*. The MIC of MM 6 ranged from 0.078 μM in *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis* to 10 μM in *B. cepacia*, *B. cereus*, and *E. cloacae*.

The antibacterial properties of MM were also assessed in a panel of *E. coli* single-gene knockouts, deleted for genes encoding different components of efflux pumps responsible for resistance to different antibiotics (Table S5). The MIC of the different single-gene knockouts was lower, equal, or superior to that of the wild-type (WT) parent strain depending on the gene deleted, with no particular trend towards resistance or sensitivity to MM treatment among the panel of strains tested (Fig. S9).

182 The ability of light-activated MM (1x MIC) to kill antibiotic-tolerant persister cells
183 (**Fig. 3A**) was investigated in the Gram-negative strains *A. baumannii*, *E. coli*, and *P.*
184 *aeruginosa*. In *S. aureus*, stationary phase cells were used in persister eradication assays
185 (14). In *A. baumannii*, treatment with MM resulted in a reduction in the levels of persisters
186 to the limit of detection in 3 min (MM 1) to 15 min (MM 3) of irradiation. The number of
187 persister cells of *E. coli* was reduced to the limit of detection in 5 min (MM 2, MM 4, MM
188 6) to 10 min (MM 1, MM 5, MM 3) of irradiation. In the case of *P. aeruginosa*, persister
189 levels were reduced to the limit of detection in 2 min (MM 1) to 15 min (MM 2) of
190 irradiation. Reduction in the number of persister cells of *S. aureus* to the limit of detection
191 was achieved in 3 min (MM 2, MM 4) to 10 min (MM 3) (**Fig. 3A**).

192 The antibiofilm potential of the most efficient MM was investigated in a 96-well
193 plate format using a combination of methods targeting different components of the biofilm
194 (15). Since preliminary experiments revealed that, for the same irradiation period, treatment
195 with 1x or 2x MIC of MM resulted in a similar reduction in biofilm biomass (**Fig. S10**), in
196 subsequent experiments irradiation time, rather than MM concentrations, was varied.

197 Mature biofilms of *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* were established and then
198 challenged with 1% DMSO or 2x MIC of MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6 followed by 405 nm
199 irradiation at 146 mW cm⁻² for 15-, 30- and 45-min. Conventional antibiotics (rifampin and
200 tobramycin) at 2x MIC were used as controls. The effect of visible light-activated MM on
201 total bacterial cell number within biofilms was assessed using the nucleic acid dye acridine
202 orange (15). Compared to untreated controls, treatment with the antibiotics tobramycin and
203 rifampin resulted in a reduction in total bacterial cell numbers of up to 43 and 64% ($p <$
204 0.01), respectively. DMSO-treated samples showed a reduction in total cell numbers of up
205 to 50% ($p <$ 0.01), while MM-treated cells showed up to 78% ($p <$ 0.01) reduction in total
206 cell number, compared to the respective untreated controls (**Fig. 3B**).

207 ATP quantification was used as a proxy of the number of metabolically active cells
208 within biofilms (15). The population of metabolically active cells was reduced by 18 to 27%
209 ($p <$ 0.05) by rifampin and tobramycin, respectively, even after 45 min of treatment, while
210 a 15-min treatment period with visible light-activated MM reduced the amount of
211 metabolically active cells by as much as 94% ($p <$ 0.01), compared to a 66% reduction ($p <$
212 0.01) in DMSO-treated samples, relatively to the respective untreated controls (**Fig. 3C**).

213 Treatment with control antibiotics resulted in a reduction in biofilm protein content
214 of up to 78% ($p <$ 0.01). The same treatment time resulted in up to 82% reduction ($p <$ 0.01)
215 in biofilm protein in DMSO-treated samples and up to 89% reduction ($p <$ 0.01) in MM-
216 treated samples, compared to untreated controls (**Fig. 3D**).

217 Treatment with the antibiotics tobramycin and rifampin resulted in a reduction of
218 biofilm biomass of up to 29% (**Fig. 3E**). Compared to untreated controls, treatment with
219 visible light-activated MM resulted in a biomass reduction of up to 99% ($p <$ 0.05), while
220 DMSO-treated samples showed a reduction in biofilm biomass of up to 49% (**Fig. 3E**).

Repeated exposure to MM does not lead to the development of resistance

The ability of cells to develop resistance to successive MM exposure was assessed by serial passaging, whereby cells surviving treatment with 0.5x MIC of the different MM followed by 5 min of irradiation with 405 nm light at 146 mW cm⁻² (43.8 J cm⁻²) were collected and subjected to 20 cycles of repeated exposure to MM. Repeated exposure to MM did not result in a change in the MIC, in contrast to the steep increase (32- to 128-fold) in the MIC through time that was observed in samples treated with conventional antibiotics (**Fig. 3F**). Importantly, mutants that evolved resistance to antibiotics did not exhibit cross-resistance to MM (**Table S6**).

MM target the cell membrane

The mechanism of action of MM was investigated using RNAseq, an array of spectrophoto- and spectrofluorimetric methods, and electron microscopy (**Fig. 1D**). All mechanism of action studies were conducted under the same irradiation conditions: 5 min of irradiation with 405 nm light at 146 mW cm⁻² (light dose of 43.8 J cm⁻²).

RNAseq was conducted on *E. coli* treated with 0.5x MIC of the most potent MM (MM 1) or 1% DMSO and 43.8 J cm⁻² of 405 nm light (**Fig. 4A**). A total of 4311 transcripts were detected by RNAseq (**Fig. 4B**). Of these, 2694 showed significantly different levels ($p < 0.05$) in MM-treated cells compared to DMSO controls. A total of 1362 transcripts were significantly more abundant in MM-treated samples, while 1332 transcripts were significantly more abundant in DMSO controls. MM 1-treated samples and DMSO controls exhibited distinct transcriptomic profiles (**Fig. 4C**), with some transcripts displaying as much as a 5-fold difference in abundance between treatments (**Fig. 4D**).

Gene ontology (GO) enrichment analysis revealed that transcripts more abundant in DMSO controls were significantly enriched ($p < 0.05$) for membrane-associated biological processes and molecular functions, including respiration and transmembrane transport (**Table S7**, **Table S8**). Transcripts more abundant in DMSO controls were also significantly enriched ($p < 0.05$) for membrane-related cellular components (**Table S9**).

Interestingly, analysis of transcripts significantly more abundant in MM-treated cells did not reveal a significant enrichment for particular biological processes, molecular functions, or cellular components, denoting the unspecific character of MM-induced cellular damage. To further understand whether the genes encoding the transcripts more abundant in MM-treated samples compared to DMSO controls play a role in susceptibility to MM, the MIC for the corresponding single-gene knockouts (**Table S10**) was assessed. No consistent trend towards resistance or sensitivity to MM treatment was observed (**Fig. S11**), suggesting no particular relevance of these genes to the cell's response to MM.

Based on the results obtained by RNAseq identifying the membrane as the major target of MM, the investigation into the mode of action of MM proceeded by examining their impact on inner and outer membrane integrity. The fluorescent probe *N*-phenyl-1-naphthylamine (NPN) was used to examine damage to the outer membrane (16). Treatment of *E. coli* with MM and 43.8 J cm⁻² of 405 nm light resulted in a concentration-dependent increase in NPN fluorescence by as much as 2.5-fold in the case of MM 6, compared to DMSO controls (**Fig. 5A**), denoting MM-induced damage to the outer membrane of the cell.

265 The effect of treatment with MM in inner membrane permeability was examined by
266 monitoring the fluorescence of propidium iodide (PI) in *E. coli* cells treated with different
267 concentrations of each MM or DMSO in the presence and absence of 405 nm light (43.8 J
268 cm^{-2}). Treatment with MM (0.5-1x MIC) resulted in an overall increase in PI fluorescence
269 (**Fig. 5B**), denoting damage to the inner membrane of the cell in MM-treated samples.

270 Treatment with MM also resulted in a significant increase in extracellular levels of
271 ATP from 4.6×10^{-10} moles in dark DMSO controls to up to 1.2×10^{-7} moles in cells
272 challenged with 1x MIC of MM **1** (**Fig. 5C**), denoting leakage of intracellular contents
273 following MM treatment.

274 Membrane damage was accompanied by dissipation of the membrane potential,
275 denoted by an increase in DiSC₃(5) fluorescence by as much as 1.9-, 1.6- and 1.3-fold
276 following treatment with 1x MIC of MM **1**, MM **5**, and MM **6**, respectively, compared to
277 DMSO controls (**Fig. 5D**). Similar trends in terms of MM-induced membrane damage (**Fig.**
278 **S12**) and loss of membrane potential (**Fig. S13**) were also observed in the Gram-positive *S.*
279 *aureus*, demonstrating that the mechanism of action of MM is not species-specific.

280 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images revealed that treatment of *E. coli*
281 with 0.5x MIC of MM **1**, MM **5**, and MM **6** and 43.8 J cm^{-2} of 405 nm light resulted in
282 substantial changes in cell morphology including the detachment of the inner membrane
283 from the cell wall, damage to peptidoglycan, distortion of the cell surface, and formation of
284 outer membrane vesicles denoting membrane and periplasmic stress (**Fig. 5E**). Scanning
285 electron microscopy (SEM) showed that, compared to DMSO controls, samples treated with
286 MM **1** displayed reduced cell size accompanied by deformation and wrinkling of the cell
287 surface. MM-treated samples also exhibited multiple pore-like deformations throughout the
288 cell surface, which were not detected in DMSO-treated cells (**Fig. 5F**).

289 *MM potentiate antibiotic action*

290 The interaction of MM with conventional antibiotics was investigated by
291 determining the MIC of different classes of antibiotics alone and following treatment of *E.*
292 *coli* with sub-MIC concentrations of visible light-activated MM (**Fig. 1D**), using a modified
293 checkerboard assay. In the case of the antibiotics gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, and ampicillin,
294 pre-treatment of cells with light-activated MM resulted in a decrease in the antibiotic MIC
295 value by 2- to 4-fold. In the case of the antibiotic novobiocin, the MIC value was drastically
296 reduced from $0.48 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in untreated cells to $0.0075 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ when cells were pre-treated
297 with MM **1** and MM **5**, and to $0.015 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in the case of pre-treatment with MM **6** (**Fig.**
298 **6A**). Calculation of the fractional inhibition concentration (FIC) index (17), revealed a
299 synergistic interaction between MM and novobiocin (FIC index ≤ 0.5), suggesting
300 potentiation (up to 64-fold) of the action of novobiocin by pre-treatment with MM (**Fig.**
301 **6B**).

302 The ability of MM to potentiate antibiotic killing was further examined by pre-
303 treating cells with 0.5x MIC of MM and 43.8 J cm^{-2} of 405 nm light prior to challenge with
304 different antibiotics for 2 h (**Fig. 6C**). On average, treatment of *E. coli* with 4x MIC of
305 different antibiotic combinations resulted in a 3-log reduction in bacterial numbers
306 compared to treatment with individual antibiotics (**Fig. 6D**). However, cells that were pre-
307 treated with sublethal concentrations of MM exhibited a 4-log reduction in bacterial
308 numbers following antibiotic challenge, compared to the treatment with individual

309 antibiotics and antibiotic combinations. The observation that pre-treatment with MM **1**, MM
310 **5**, and MM **6** resulted in a substantial increase in intracellular tetracycline fluorescence,
311 compared to DMSO-treated samples (**Fig. 6E**) further indicates that MM potentiates
312 antibiotic killing by permeabilizing the cell membrane and facilitating access of antibiotics
313 to their intracellular targets.

314 The ability of pre-treatment with sublethal MM concentrations to potentiate
315 antibiotic action was further investigated in *P. aeruginosa* treated with sub-MIC
316 concentrations of the three most potent MM (MM **1**, MM **5**, and MM **6**) and then challenged
317 with increasing concentrations of the antibiotic vancomycin. Due to its large size,
318 vancomycin (~1450 Da) usually cannot cross the outer membrane of Gram-negative
319 bacteria (18). However, treatment with sub-MIC concentrations of MM resulted in
320 increased susceptibility of *P. aeruginosa* to vancomycin, denoted by inhibition of growth in
321 checkerboard plates (**Fig. 6F**). Accordingly, *P. aeruginosa* cells pre-treated with 0.25x MIC
322 of the different visible light-activated MM were killed in 60 to 150 min of treatment with
323 vancomycin (**Fig. 6G**).

324 *Therapeutic doses of MM mitigate infection-associated mortality in vivo*

325 The toxicity of MM to mammalian cells was originally investigated by examining
326 the light dose-dependent effects of different concentrations of the most potent MM (MM **1**,
327 MM **5**, and MM **6**) in human embryonic kidney cells (HEK). The results revealed a
328 reduction in viability of HEK cells with increasing concentration of MM and increasing
329 light dose (**Fig. S14**). The safety of MM was further examined in both HEK cells and normal
330 human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs), by determining the MM concentration resulting in a
331 50% reduction in the viability of mammalian cells (IC₅₀) following 5 min of irradiation at
332 146 mW cm⁻² (43.8 J cm⁻²), the same experimental conditions used to determine the bacterial
333 MIC (**Table S11**). For NHDFs the IC₅₀ ranged from 5 μM for MM **1** to 10 μM for MM **5**
334 and MM **6**. For HEK cells, the IC₅₀ was 5 μM for the three MM tested. Based on these
335 results, a concentration of 1x the MIC of each MM (**Table S3**) was used for subsequent *in*
336 *vivo* experiments.

337 The *in vivo* antibacterial activity of MM was investigated in a burn wound infection
338 model of the invertebrate *Galleria mellonella* (19). Following the generation of a burn
339 wound in the worm, wounds were infected with either the Gram-positive *S. aureus* or the
340 Gram-negative *A. baumannii*. Infected wounds were then treated with 1% DMSO, 1x MIC
341 of conventional antibiotics (polymyxin B in the case of *A. baumannii* infection and
342 tobramycin in the case of *S. aureus* infection), 1% DMSO, or 1x MIC of MM **1**, MM **5**, or
343 MM **6** for each bacterial strain and 43.8 J cm⁻² of 405 nm light (**Fig. 7A**). The survival of
344 worms under different treatments was monitored for up to 7 days post-treatment.

345 All (100%) worms infected with *A. baumannii* and treated with 1% DMSO only (no
346 light) died by day 6 post-treatment (**Fig. 7B**). Treatment with 1x MIC of polymyxin B
347 attenuated mortality after 7 days to 69% ($p < 0.0001$, **Table S12**), while treatment with MM
348 attenuated mortality after 7 days to 40-60% ($p < 0.0001$). In the case of worms infected with
349 *S. aureus* and treated with 1% DMSO (no light), 100% mortality was observed 7 days post-
350 treatment. Treatment with 1x MIC of tobramycin mitigated mortality at 7 days to 33%,
351 while treatment with MM mitigated mortality after 7 days to 17-25% ($p < 0.0001$).

Discussion

Here we describe an antibacterial therapy based on the use of synthetic visible light-activated MM that kill bacteria by mechanical damage. At therapeutic doses, synthetic MM were activated by visible light to kill Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), within minutes, vastly outperforming conventional antibiotics (**Fig. 2A-B**).

Besides exponentially growing cells, MM also rapidly eliminated persister cells (**Fig. 3A**). Persister cells are defined as transiently antibiotic-tolerant fractions of bacterial populations that are metabolically inactive or dormant (20). In this phenotypic state, the biosynthetic processes targeted by conventional antibiotics are inactive or significantly attenuated, making them highly tolerant to conventional antibiotics that typically affect growing bacteria with an active metabolism (21–23).

MM were also able to significantly reduce the cell number and biomass of established biofilms of *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* (**Fig. 3B-E**). Similar to persister cells, biofilms are considered resistant phenotypes, characterized by the presence of a heterogeneous dense extracellular polymeric matrix that includes extracellular DNA, proteins, and polysaccharides in which high densities of microbial cells are entrapped (24). This complex milieu provides a barrier to antibiotic diffusion and penetration, making biofilm-associated infections frequently refractory to conventional antimicrobial therapy (25–27). However, the irradiation conditions necessary for complete elimination of biofilms are much higher than those safe for mammalian cells (**Table S11**), and at the extended irradiation times necessary to completely reduce biofilm biomass (up to 45 min), an effect of temperature cannot be excluded.

Contrary to conventional antibiotics, repeated exposure to MM in serial passage experiments (28) was not accompanied by a change in MIC value (**Fig. 3F**), suggesting a low propensity for the development of resistance to MM therapy across different bacteria.

Since MM resistant mutants could not be isolated, the mechanism of action of these new molecules was investigated using gene expression analysis *via* RNAseq, and an array of spectrophoto- and spectrofluorimetric methods, and electron microscopy in *E. coli*. MM- and DMSO-treated cells displayed strikingly distinct transcriptomic profiles (**Fig. 4C**). Transcripts significantly more abundant in DMSO-treated cells compared to MM-treated cells were overwhelming enriched for membrane-associated processes (**Table S7-9**), identifying the membrane as the major target of MM. Increased fluorescence of dyes used to monitor damage to the inner and outer bacterial membrane (**Fig. 5A-B**) further demonstrated that the mechanism of action of MM involves unspecific, widespread damage to the cell envelope. Membrane damage was followed by leakage of intracellular components, denoted by increased levels of extracellular ATP (**Fig. 5C**), and loss of the ability to sustain the membrane potential, evidenced by increased fluorescence of the membrane potential dye DiSC₃(5) (**Fig. 5D**). Electron microscopy revealed extensive damage to the cell ultrastructure following MM treatment, particularly at the level of the membrane and cell wall, including the presence of physical deformities reminiscent of holes in the cell surface that were absent in DMSO controls (**Fig. 5E-F**).

These results suggest that the mode of action of MM is distinct from that of membrane-targeting, pore-forming antibiotics such as nisin or daptomycin, which involve

docking to specific binding sites in the membrane and the oligomerization of the antibiotic molecule to form a pore or ion channel (29, 30). Resistance to such antibiotics has been reported and attributed to altered cell wall and cell membrane composition and function in resistant mutants (31, 32). The fact that MM were able to rapidly kill a range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including antibiotic-resistant strains and efflux knockouts, suggests that the antibacterial action of MM does not involve binding to specific elements within the bacterial envelope. Rather, the mechano-bactericidal action of MM via physical membrane disruption is unlike any other antibacterial modality of which we are aware. This molecular-level generalized, unspecific membrane damage can also possibly account for the ability of MM to efficiently eradicate persisters, which are particularly susceptible to membrane-targeting agents (33). Further studies using MM coupled with fluorescent molecules will be useful in visualizing the precise positioning of the MM within the cell membrane and whether, once inside the cell, they may bind and destroy other intracellular targets.

A mode of action that involves physical membrane disruption may also explain the undetectable levels of resistance after repeated exposure to MM (Fig. 3F). A low propensity for resistance development could also be explained by the involvement of two distinct modes of action in the antibacterial activity of MM: (1) physical membrane damage resulting from fast rotation of MM following light activation, and (2) antibacterial effects of blue light. Blue light (400-490 nm) has well known antibacterial properties (34–37) and also shows a low propensity for resistance development (37, 38). The antibacterial mechanism of action of blue light appears to involve the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and subsequent oxidative damage to biomolecules (39–41). However, under our experimental setup, a significant difference in ROS levels in MM-treated cells and DMSO-treated cells was not detected (Fig. S15). Also, the MM-induced inactivation profiles of *E. coli* treated with ROS scavengers prior to irradiation were similar to those of untreated cells (Fig. S16), suggesting that ROS do not play a significant role in MM-induced bacterial killing. In fact, ROS quenching by the central twisted carbon-carbon double bond characteristic of MM was previously reported (42).

Importantly, antibacterial effects were only observed in MM-treated cells that were irradiated, but not in those kept in the dark, denoting the importance of light for the antibacterial effects of MM. Since the irradiation conditions used for most experiments (5 min of irradiation with 405 nm light at 146 mW cm^{-2}), did not result in a significant increase in temperature, and the temperature variations in samples treated with fast antibacterial MM ($23.9 \pm 1.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and slow MM ($24.4 \pm 1.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) without antibacterial activity were similar (Fig. S17), temperature alone cannot account for the antibacterial effects of MM.

Also, irradiated MM maintained their integrity and biological activity and did not undergo photodecomposition, as evidenced by NMR spectra before and after irradiation displaying only changes in isomer ratios but the absence of new aromatic signals (Fig. S18). Sustained antibacterial activity of extensively pre-irradiated MM (Fig. S19) further excludes phototoxicity as the mechanism of action of MM.

Finally, slow MM (10^{-3} Hz) chemically analogous to antibacterial MM ($\approx 3 \text{ MHz}$) did not exhibit antibacterial activity (Fig. S3), demonstrating the importance of fast mechanical rotation for the antibacterial properties of MM.

441 Taken together, these results indicate that, under the experimental conditions
442 examined, MM-induced antibacterial effects can be attributed to the rapid drilling-like
443 unidirectional rotation of MM following light activation, whereby the rotor portion of the
444 molecule spins around the central olefinic bond (**Fig. 1B**) propelling the molecule through
445 the membrane (**Fig. 1C**). Subsequent leakage of cell contents and loss of membrane
446 potential eventually culminate in bacterial cell death.

447 The reduced permeability of the Gram-negative membrane represents an important
448 challenge for antibacterial therapy by posing a barrier that limits antibiotic entrance to the
449 cell (43, 44). In this work, we observed that, besides their direct antibacterial properties,
450 MM were able to potentiate the killing of *E. coli* by traditional antibiotics, as demonstrated
451 by (1) a reduction of antibiotic MIC values when antibiotic treatment was preceded by
452 exposure of cells to sublethal doses of MM (**Fig. 6A**) and, (2) enhanced killing by antibiotics
453 following pre-exposure of cells to sublethal MM (**Fig. 6D**). Increased intracellular
454 tetracycline fluorescent signal in cells pre-treated with visible light-activated MM (**Fig. 6E**),
455 suggests that the enhanced antibiotic killing of cells pre-treated with MM is a result of MM-
456 induced cell permeabilization and increased accessibility of antibiotics to their intracellular
457 targets.

458 This effect was not only observed in *E. coli* but also in the opportunistic pathogen
459 *P. aeruginosa*. Due to its hydrophilicity and large size, vancomycin (~1450 Da) usually
460 cannot cross the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria (18). However, *P. aeruginosa*
461 challenged with sublethal concentrations of fast light-activated MM displayed substantial
462 growth inhibition following subsequent treatment with vancomycin (**Fig. 6F**) and were
463 completely killed in as little as 60 min by the otherwise ineffective vancomycin (**Fig. 6G**).
464 These results demonstrate the ability of MM to permeabilize the Gram-negative outer
465 membrane to substances that would otherwise be excluded, including typical Gram-positive
466 antibiotics, like vancomycin.

467 The results obtained in this study demonstrate that, by permeabilizing the Gram-
468 negative outer membrane and improving the accessibility of antibiotics to intracellular
469 targets, MM exert an antibiotic co-adjuvant action. Future work should aim to identify other
470 antibacterial molecules whose action can be potentiated by visible light active MM-induced
471 membrane permeabilization.

472 The safety of MM to mammalian cells was investigated *in vitro* in two mammalian
473 cell lines subjected to the same irradiation conditions used to determine the bacterial MIC.
474 The intensity (146 mW cm^{-2}) and dose/fluence (43.8 J cm^{-2}) of 405 nm light used throughout
475 most of this study are comparable, or lower, to those previously shown to be safe for
476 mammalian cells *in vitro* and *in vivo* (40, 45–48). The proximity of the IC50 and MIC
477 (**Table S11**), particularly in *A. baumannii*, demonstrates the broad destructive capabilities
478 of MM, previously reported for UV- activated MM (11, 49).

479 Given these safety concerns, the invertebrate infection model *Galleria mellonella*
480 was used to investigate the *in vivo* anti-infective capabilities of MM. *G. mellonella* is a well-
481 established, inexpensive, and low maintenance model of fungal and bacterial infections (50–
482 53). While insects like *G. mellonella* do not have an adaptive immune response and cannot
483 generate antibodies, their complex innate immune system shows some similarities to that of
484 mammals (54). Importantly, correlations between immune responses to pathogens in *G.*

485 *mellonella* and mice demonstrate that results obtained using this invertebrate model can
486 provide significant insights into the mammalian response (55–57).

487 Due to their location, skin wounds, such as burns, are particularly amenable to light-
488 mediated antimicrobial therapies. Systemic antimicrobials have limited efficiency in the
489 treatment of such localized infections due to poor blood flow to these areas and the presence
490 of dead tissue (58, 59) while potentially contributing to the development of resistance in
491 non-target organisms (59). A *G. mellonella* burn wound infection model was recently
492 described (19).

493 In this work, burn wounds of *G. mellonella* were infected with two of the major
494 bacterial pathogens typically associated with burn wounds, *A. baumannii* and *S. aureus* (60,
495 61). Treatment of infected worms with visible light-activated MM mitigated the mortality
496 associated with infection by both *A. baumannii* and *S. aureus* (**Fig. 7B**). Mortality mitigation
497 by MM (up to 83%) was similar or superior to that of conventional antibiotics. These results
498 demonstrate the potential of MM in the treatment of localized bacterial infections, despite
499 the small therapeutic window.

500 Future next-generation MM need to not only be potent antibacterials but display
501 improved selectivity towards bacteria with minimal damage to mammalian cells, for
502 instance by increasing the number of positive charges within MM to enhance their affinity
503 towards the negatively-charged bacterial membrane but not the more neutrally-charged
504 mammalian membrane (62). Bacteria-specific peptide addends (63) linked to either the
505 stator or the rotor portion of the molecule can also be employed for the targeted killing of
506 bacteria by MM. Alternatively, safe and effective antibacterial effects can be achieved by
507 combining light-activated MM and conventional antibiotics, whereby bactericidal effects
508 can be exerted at sublethal MM concentrations, circumventing potential MM toxicity.

Materials and Methods

Synthetic Chemistry

Details on the synthesis and characterization of the MM used in this study are provided in Supplementary Information.

Preparation of cells for irradiation experiments

Cells from glycerol stocks maintained at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ were streaked onto LB agar plates to get single isolated colonies. One single colony was picked up from the plate and grown overnight in 5 mL of filter-sterilized LB media in a 50 mL falcon tube (220 rpm at 30 or 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ depending on the strain). The following day, 1 mL of the overnight culture was added to 50 mL of filter-sterilized LB media in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask and incubated until an optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600}) of approximately 1. A volume of 500 μL of this culture was diluted into 50 mL of fresh filter-sterilized LB media and centrifuged for 15 min at 5000 rpm, 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Afterward, the pellet was resuspended in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) to a final $\text{OD}_{600} \approx 0.05$.

Irradiation experiments

The appropriate volume of an MM stock at 8 mM necessary to achieve a concentration ranging from 0.3125 to 40 μM was pipetted into a 2 mL microcentrifuge tube to which 1 mL of cell suspension prepared as previously described was added. Corresponding negative controls (DMSO only) were prepared in the same way. The mixture was gently mixed by pipetting and incubated in the dark at 30 or 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, depending on the strain, for 30 min with agitation (220 rpm). Afterward, MM- or DMSO-treated cells were dispensed in one well of a 24-well plate positioned in the center of the light beam (405 nm LED Light, Prizmatix, UHP-F-5-405) placed at the appropriate distance necessary to achieve the desired light intensity of 304 mW cm^{-2} , 146 mW cm^{-2} or 87 mW cm^{-2} , as measured with a handheld digital power meter console coupled to an S415C thermal power sensor head (Thorlabs, Newton, MA, USA). The temperature during irradiation was monitored using a thermocouple probe (Model SC-TT-K-30-36-PP; Omega Engineering, Inc., Stamford, CT, USA). Samples were agitated during irradiation. Dark controls were prepared as previously described except that no irradiation was provided.

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)

For MIC determination, samples treated with a range of concentrations of the different MM, as described above and were irradiated one at a time for 5 min at 146 mW cm^{-2} (43.8 J cm^{-2}), after which irradiated aliquots were collected and inoculated into 1 mL MHB in a 2 mL microcentrifuge tube. Samples were incubated overnight at 30 or 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, depending on the strain, without agitation. Corresponding non-irradiated samples and negative controls (without bacteria) were also included. The following day, cultures were inspected for growth and the MIC was identified. The experimental procedure used to determine the MIC of visible light-activated MM is schematically depicted in **Fig. S2**.

552 For time-kill experiments, 50 μL aliquots in triplicate of samples treated with 2x
553 MIC determined as described above were collected at different time points (0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and
554 5, 10 and 15 min) following 405 nm irradiation at different light intensities (87, 146 and
555 304 mW cm^{-2} , corresponding to a distance between sample and light source of 20 cm, 15
556 cm, and 10 cm, respectively). For light dose-dependency experiments, samples were
557 exposed to different concentrations of the most potent MM (MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6) and
558 irradiated with 0, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 40, and 80 J cm^{-2} . Serial dilutions of irradiated cell
559 suspensions were prepared in PBS. A volume of 10 μL of the appropriate serial dilutions
560 was spot-plated onto LB agar plates. Following overnight incubation at 30 or 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$,
561 depending on the strain, bacterial viability was assessed as colony forming units (CFU) per
562 mL. Results were expressed as $\log(N/N_0)$ whereby N is the CFU mL^{-1} at each irradiation
563 time point and N_0 is the initial CFU mL^{-1} of the corresponding sample. Only dilutions that
564 yielded 10–100 colonies were counted.

565 *Preparation and eradication of persister and persister-like cells*

566 Persisters of *A. baumannii* and *P. aeruginosa* were generated by growing cell
567 cultures to late-stationary phase for 16 h at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, followed by treatment with ciprofloxacin
568 (10-fold MIC) for 4 h to kill non-persistent cells (64). Persister cells of *E. coli* were prepared
569 by adding ampicillin (100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) to exponential-phase cells (OD_{600} of ≈ 0.8) followed by
570 continuous agitation for another 3 h, as previously described (14). In the case of *S. aureus*,
571 almost all stationary-phase are considered to be persistent (14). *S. aureus* cells were grown
572 at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 220 rpm in LB broth to an OD_{600} of 0.3. Cells were then diluted 1:1000 in
573 25 mL LB and grown for 16 h at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 220 rpm in 250 mL flasks. Ampicillin-tolerant
574 or stationary phase persister cells of *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, respectively, were collected and
575 resuspended in PBS and then challenged with 1x MIC of MM or 1% DMSO followed by
576 irradiation at 405 nm at a dose of 146 mW cm^{-2} , as described for exponential phase cells.
577 Antibiotic controls (2x and 4x MIC) were processed in the same way, except that no light
578 was provided. At specified time points (0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, 10 and 15 min), 50- μL aliquots
579 were removed, serially diluted and spot-plated onto LB agar plates to determine colony-
580 forming units per mL (CFU mL^{-1}). Only dilutions that yielded 10–100 colonies were
581 counted. Results were expressed as $\log(N/N_0)$ whereby N is the CFU mL^{-1} at each
582 irradiation time point and N_0 is the initial CFU mL^{-1} of the corresponding sample. Only
583 dilutions that yielded 10–100 colonies were counted.

584 *Antibiofilm potential of visible light-activated MM*

585 The antibiofilm potential of the most potent MM (MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6) was
586 assessed in a 96 well plate format using a combination of methods targeting different
587 components of the biofilm (15): acridine orange was used to quantify the total bacteria cell
588 number, ATP quantification was used to quantify metabolically active cells within the
589 biofilm, crystal violet was used to quantify biofilm biomass, and fluorescein isothiocyanate
590 was used to quantify total protein in the biofilm matrix. This combination of methods is
591 effective at evaluating the antibiofilm potential of chemicals (15). *P. aeruginosa* and *S.*
592 *aureus* were grown overnight in tryptic soy broth (TSB) medium. The overnight cultures
593 were diluted in 1:100 in fresh media and 100 μL aliquots were distributed in a 96-well plate.
594 After 24 h of static growth at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, planktonic cells were removed by inverting the plate
595 onto a stack of paper towels, and the biofilm was washed three times with PBS. After

596 washing, MM 1, MM 5, or MM 6 were added at 2x MIC to the biofilm and incubated
597 statically in the dark for 60 min. The biofilm was then irradiated for 15, 30, or 45 min at
598 146 mW cm⁻². For the determination of the total bacterial number, acridine orange solution
599 (2% in H₂O) diluted 1:100 in Walpole's buffer (27.2 g L⁻¹ sodium acetate trihydrate,
600 adjusted to pH 4 with glacial acetic acid) was added to the wells. Following a 15 min
601 incubation, the biofilm was washed three times with 0.9 % NaCl, thoroughly resuspended
602 in 100 µL 0.9 % NaCl, and fluorescence intensity (excitation: 485 nm, emission: 528 nm)
603 was measured in a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT, USA) (15).

604 For quantification of viable cells in biofilms, following the addition of 100 µL
605 hundred microliters of TSB to each well, bacteria were detached from the biofilm by
606 thorough mixing, after which 100 µL of BacTiter-Glo™ reagent, prepared according to the
607 manufacturer's instructions, was added to each well. After a 5 min incubation, the
608 luminescence intensity was measured in a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc,
609 Winooski, VT, USA) (15).

610 For total biofilm protein quantification, 250 µL of FITC solution (20 µg mL⁻¹) was
611 added to each well. Following a 30 min incubation, the biofilm was thoroughly washed with
612 0.9 % NaCl and then resuspended in 100 µL ddH₂O. Fluorescence intensity was measured
613 (excitation: 485 nm, emission: 528 nm) in a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc,
614 Winooski, VT, USA)(15).

615 For total biofilm biomass quantification, 100 µL of TSB media was added to the
616 irradiated biofilm. Following 24 h of recovery at 37 °C, plates were again inverted onto a
617 stack of paper towels and the biofilm was then washed with water by submersion of the
618 plate. The washed biofilm was stained with a 0.1% solution of crystal violet in water. After
619 15 min of staining the plate was rinsed 3 times with water, and then blotted on a stack of
620 paper towels. After overnight drying of the plate, 30% acetic acid in water was added to
621 solubilize the crystal violet for 15 min. The solubilized crystal violet was transferred to a
622 new flat-bottom microtiter plate and the absorbance at 550 nm was quantified in a
623 microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT, USA), using 30% acetic acid in
624 water as the blank (65). Unirradiated samples were used as controls. Control antibiotics
625 rifampin (*P. aeruginosa*) and tobramycin (*S. aureus*) at 2x MIC were also included and
626 processed as described for MM.

627 *Resistance development*

628 Isolation of MM-resistant mutants of *E. coli*, *A. baumannii*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S.*
629 *aureus* was attempted by irradiating cell suspensions treated with 4x MIC of the different
630 MM for 5 min at 146 mW cm⁻² (43.8 J cm⁻²). No visible colonies could be obtained for any
631 of the strains tested.

632 For resistance development by sequential passaging (66), *A. baumannii*, *E. coli*, *P.*
633 *aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* cells in exponential phase were collected and processed as
634 described for MIC determination. Cells were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h after which they
635 were inspected for growth. Cells able to grow at 0.5x MIC were collected and re-challenged
636 with a range of MM concentrations and then irradiated. The antibiotics ciprofloxacin and
637 gentamicin (for Gram-negatives) or ciprofloxacin and tobramycin (for *S. aureus*) were used
638 as controls.

640 Three independent, well-isolated colonies of *E. coli* were cultured to mid-log phase
641 in MHB media. Cells were collected and resuspended in PBS (1x) to an OD₆₀₀ of ≈ 0.05 .
642 Cells were treated with 0.5x MIC of MM 1, or 1% DMSO in the dark for 30 min. Cells were
643 then irradiated for 5 min at 146 mW cm⁻² (43.8 J cm⁻²). Bacterial cells were collected onto
644 a 0.2 μ m PES filter by low vacuum filtration. Two volumes of RNeasy Protect (Qiagen,
645 Valencia, CA) were added to the cells, and the samples were then centrifuged at 5000 g for
646 25 min at 4 °C to pellet cells. RNA was isolated using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen,
647 Valencia, CA) per the manufacturer's instructions. RNA sequencing (RNAseq) and data
648 analysis were performed by DNA Link Inc. (Seoul, Republic of Korea). RNA-Seq libraries
649 were constructed by using TruSeq Stranded Total RNA with Ribo-Zero Plus rRNA
650 Depletion Kit and sequenced on the Illumina NovaSeq6000 platform (Illumina, San Diego,
651 CA) in the 100 nt, paired-end configuration. From each sample, an average of 70 million
652 reads was obtained. For gene expression analysis, reads were trimmed with cutadapt (67)
653 and aligned to the reference genome of *Escherichia coli* str. K-12 substr. MG1655
654 (NC_000913) using EDGE-pro pipeline with default setting. Differential expression
655 analysis was performed with DESeq2 in Bioconductor (68). Gene annotation was performed
656 using an in-house script based on NCBI reference annotations.

657 Gene ontology (GO) enrichment analysis of the transcripts displaying significant
658 differences ($p < 0.05$) in abundance between MM- and DMSO-treated cells was performed
659 using Panther (<http://pantherdb.org/>) using the Fisher's Exact test. Results were corrected
660 for the false discovery rate (FDR).

661 *Outer Membrane Permeability*

662 The impact of treatment with MM on the outer membrane permeability of *E. coli*
663 was determined using the *N*-phenyl-1-naphthylamine (NPN) uptake assay as previously
664 described (16). The pore-forming antibiotic nisin was used as a positive control for
665 membrane damage. Cells were washed and resuspended in buffer (5 mM HEPES, 5 mM
666 glucose, pH 7.4) and treated with different concentrations of MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6, or
667 1% DMSO. Following irradiation as described for MIC determination, 100 μ L of the
668 bacteria suspension was mixed with NPN (final concentration: 2 μ g mL⁻¹) in a 96-well black
669 plate. NPN fluorescence was then monitored (Excitation: 350 nm, Emission: 420 nm) as a
670 function of time using a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT, USA).
671 Results were expressed as relative fluorescent units (RFU) corrected for fluorescence in the
672 absence of NPN and in the absence of cells.

673 *Inner Membrane Permeability*

674 *E. coli* cells were prepared as previously described and treated with a range of
675 concentrations of MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6 and irradiated with 405 nm light at an intensity
676 of 146 mW cm⁻². Nisin was used as a positive control. Following irradiation, propidium
677 iodide (PI) was added to the cells at a final concentration of 2 μ g mL⁻¹ (69). After 30 min of
678 incubation, 200 μ L of bacterial suspension was added into a black 96-well plate and the
679 time-dependent progression of fluorescence intensity (excitation: 535 nm, emission:
680 620 nm) was recorded in a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT,
681 USA). Results were expressed RFU corrected for fluorescence in the absence of cells and
682 in the absence of PI.

684 The depolarization of the cytoplasmic membrane of *E. coli* by MM was assessed
685 using the membrane potential-sensitive cyanine dye DiSC₃(5) (70). Briefly, exponential-
686 phase bacteria were washed and resuspended in 5 mM HEPES–20 mM glucose buffer (pH
687 7.2) to an optical density of 0.05. This cell suspension was incubated with 100 mM KCl (to
688 equilibrate cytoplasmic and external K⁺ concentration) and 0.4 μM DiSC₃(5) until
689 stabilization of the fluorescent signal. Cells were then incubated with different
690 concentrations of MM and irradiated as described for MIC determination. CCCP was used
691 as a positive control (71). Cells were then transferred to a black 96 well and the fluorescent
692 signal was monitored (excitation: 622 nm, emission: 670 nm) using a microplate reader
693 (BioTek Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT, USA). Results were expressed as RFU corrected
694 for fluorescence in the absence of DiSC₃(5) and in the absence of cells.

695 *Extracellular ATP*

696 Intracellular content leakage following treatment with MM was determined by
697 quantifying extracellular ATP (72). Following irradiation in the presence of different
698 concentrations of MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6, or 1% DMSO, *E. coli* cells were centrifuged at
699 13,000 g for 5 min. Supernatants were recovered and stored at -20 °C for ATP analysis.
700 ATP analysis was conducted using the luminescence-based BacTiter-Glo™ assay
701 (Promega) per the manufacturer's instructions. Nisin was used as a positive control. The
702 levels of ATP in supernatants were derived *via* a standard curve of ATP standards from 1
703 nM to 1 μM. Luminescence measurements of ATP standards and culture supernatants were
704 measured in triplicate on a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT,
705 USA). Results were expressed as relative light units (RLU) corrected for fluorescence in the
706 absence of cells.

707 *Electron Microscopy*

708 *E. coli* was cultured to mid-log phase in MHB media. Cells were collected and
709 resuspended in PBS (1x) to an OD₆₀₀ of ≈ 0.05. Cells were treated with 0.5x MIC of MM
710 1, or 1% DMSO in the dark for 30 min. Cells were then irradiated for 5 min at 146 mW cm⁻²
711 (43.8 J cm⁻²) after which cells were fixed with Karnovsky's fixative (73), and post-fixed
712 with 1% osmium, and dehydrated with a series of ethanol washes. For TEM, samples were
713 embedded in epoxy resin (PolyBed 812; Polysciences, Inc., Warrington, PA, United States)
714 after dehydration in a graduated 50–100% ethanol concentration series of washes. Ultrathin
715 sections (65 nm) were cut using a Leica EM UC7 ultramicrotome (Leica Microsystems,
716 Wetzlar, Germany) and post-stained with uranyl acetate and lead citrate. Specimens were
717 observed using a JEOL JEM2100 TEM (Hitachi Corporation, Japan) operating at an
718 accelerating voltage of 80 kV. For SEM, following ethanol dehydration samples were
719 critical point dried using a Leica EM CPD300 (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany),
720 sputter-coated with 10 nm of gold, and imaged with an FEI Apreo SEM (FEI Apreo,
721 ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) using a secondary electron detector.

722 *Interaction with antibiotics*

723 To evaluate synergy between conventional antibiotics and MM in *E. coli*, the
724 fractional inhibitory concentration (FIC) index (17) was determined using a modified
725 checkerboard microtiter test in an 8-by-8 well configuration. Briefly, *E. coli* cell

suspensions were prepared as described for MIC determination with an increasing concentration (0.1 – 40 μM) of the different MM, followed by irradiation for 5 min at 146 mW cm^{-2} . The irradiated cell suspensions were collected and distributed along the x-axis of a 96-well plate according to a gradient of increasing concentration, followed by the addition of a gradient of increasing concentration of antibiotic (0.00125 – 1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) along the y-axis of the plate to the irradiated cells. MHB was then added to each well of the plate and the plate was incubated at 37 °C with shaking at 220 rpm for 18 h under aerobic conditions. Bacterial growth was assessed by measuring the OD_{600} in a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT, USA). The FIC was calculated after dividing the MIC of each antibiotic in combination with different MM by the MIC of the antibiotic alone. The FIC index, obtained by adding both FICs, was interpreted as indicating a synergistic effect if it was ≤ 0.5 , as additive or indifferent if it was > 0.5 and ≤ 2.0 , and as antagonistic if it was > 2.0 (17).

In order to evaluate the ability of pre-treatment with subinhibitory concentrations of MM to potentiate killing by antibiotics, *E. coli* were prepared as described for MIC determination and treated with 0.5x MIC of each MM (MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6) or 1% DMSO followed by 5-min irradiation at 146 mW cm^{-2} . Irradiated cell suspensions were then collected and challenged with 4x MIC of the antibiotics gentamicin, novobiocin, ciprofloxacin, and ampicillin. Following preparation of the appropriate serial dilutions, samples were spot plated onto LB agar plates and the number of CFU was determined. Non-irradiated, antibiotic-treated (4x MIC) cell suspensions were similarly processed.

To evaluate the ability of pre-treatment with MM to potentiate killing by vancomycin, *P. aeruginosa* cell suspensions were prepared as described for the MIC assessment and treated with a range of concentrations (0 to 1x MIC) of the different antibacterial MM (MM 1, MM 5 and MM 6) and irradiated for 5 min with 146 mW cm^{-2} of 405 nm light. Following irradiation, cells were collected and distributed along the x-axis of a 96-well plate according to a gradient of increasing concentration, after which vancomycin was added according to a gradient of increasing concentration (0 to 40 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) along the y-axis of the plate to the irradiated cells. MHB was then added to each well of the plate and the plate was incubated at 37 °C with shaking at 220 rpm for 18 h under aerobic conditions. Bacterial growth was assessed by measuring the OD_{600} in a microplate reader (BioTek Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT, USA). For time-kill experiments, *P. aeruginosa* cell suspensions prepared as previously described were treated with 0.25x MIC of the different MM (MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6) and irradiated for 5 min with 146 mW cm^{-2} of 405 nm light. Vancomycin was then added (final concentration of 10, 20, and 40 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and survival (CFU per mL) was monitored every 30 min for 4 h (240 min), as previously described. Controls treated with vancomycin only, MM only, and DMSO plus vancomycin were also included.

Tetracycline uptake

The ability of pre-treatment with subinhibitory concentrations of MM to potentiate antibiotic killing was further evaluated by monitoring the fluorescence of tetracycline uptake. *E. coli* were prepared as described for MIC determination and treated with 0.5x MIC of each MM (MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6) or 1% DMSO followed by 5-min irradiation at 146 mW cm^{-2} . Irradiated cell suspensions were then collected, and tetracycline (128 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ final concentration) was added. A volume of 100 μL per well of tetracycline amended cell suspension was transferred to a black 96-well plate and fluorescence was read every 5 min

772 for 60 min at room temperature in a microplate reader (Ex: 405 nm, Em: 535 nm) (BioTek
773 Instruments Inc, Winooski, VT, USA). Results were expressed as RFU corrected for
774 fluorescence in the absence of cells.

775 *Toxicity profiling and therapeutic index calculation*

776 Biocompatibility of MM with primary NHDF and HEK293T cells was assessed
777 using the CellTiter-Glo® Luminescent Cell Viability Assay (Promega), per the
778 manufacturer's instructions. The MM concentrations that reduced cell viability by 50%
779 (IC50) were identified and the therapeutic index was calculated as the ratio between the
780 IC50 and the MIC at a light intensity of 146 mW cm⁻². For light dose-dependency
781 experiments, HEK cells were treated with different concentrations of the most potent MM
782 (MM 1, MM 5, and MM 6) and irradiated with 0, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 40, and 80 J cm⁻².

783 *Animal infection model*

784 Animal studies were conducted in the burn wound model *Galleria mellonella*
785 recently described (19). Larvae were purchased from a commercial source at a stage in their
786 life cycle where they do not need to be fed. Larvae were sorted into Petri dishes lined with
787 Whatman filter paper (Fisher Scientific, Pittsburg, PA) and stored at 4 °C until use. The
788 larval bodies were sterilized with 70% ethanol. The burn was generated using a soldering
789 iron (Weller WE1010 ESD-Safe Digital 70-Watt Soldering Station, 120V, Weller
790 Company, Easton, PA, USA) to achieve a consistent burn area of ≈ 2 mm² in the middle
791 section of the back of larvae. This location was chosen so the wound could be easily
792 visualized without having to physically manipulate the larvae. Immediately post-burn, the
793 wound was inoculated with 10 μL of 1:10 dilution of an overnight culture of *A. baumannii*
794 or *S. aureus*. Any larva who showed distress or leakage of hemolymph after the burn process
795 was immediately euthanized by incubating at -20 °C for 20 min to minimize suffering.
796 Following overnight incubation at 37 °C for the establishment of infection, 10 μL of (1)
797 different MM at 1x MIC, (2) antibiotics polymixin B in the case of *A. baumannii* or
798 tobramycin in the case of *S. aureus*, or (3) 1% DMSO were applied to the wound. Following
799 a 30 min incubation period in the dark, larvae were physically restrained, covered with an
800 opaque material, leaving only the wound exposed, and then irradiated for 5 min with 146
801 mW cm⁻² of 405 nm light (43.8 J cm⁻²). In order to minimize any potential temperature
802 effects, a constant flow of 0.2 μm pore-size-filtered air was provided to the surface of the
803 worm. Dark 1% DMSO controls were also included. The mortality of larvae post-treatment
804 was monitored for up to 7 days. Mortality was recorded by complete melanization of the
805 larval body and complete loss of motility. A brief overview of the protocol is schematically
806 depicted in **Fig. 7A**.

809 Unless otherwise mentioned, the arithmetic mean and the standard error of the mean
810 across multiple biological and technical replicas were used as the measures of center and
811 spread. The particular numbers of replicates for each experiment type are included in the
812 respective figure legends, where appropriate. Unless otherwise noted, all statistical analyses
813 were performed using GraphPad Prism 8.0 (San Diego, CA, USA). When appropriate, data
814 were min-max normalized. Depending on the sample size, data normality was assessed
815 using an Anderson-Darling normality test, D'Agostino-Pearson omnibus normality test,
816 Shapiro-Wilk normality test, or Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test with Dallal-
817 Wilkinson-Lilliefor's test for p-value. Comparisons between two groups were conducted
818 using a t-test for parametric data, or a Mann-Whitney U test for non-parametric data.
819 Multiple group comparisons were performed using ANOVA or a Kruskal-Wallis test with
820 Dunn's multiple comparisons test. A Mantel-Cox test was used to determine the statistical
821 significance in *Galleria mellonella* survival assays. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered
822 statistically significant. Where appropriate, asterisks are used to denote the significance of
823 differences. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$. Unless otherwise noted,
824 all figures were generated in GraphPad Prism 8.0 (San Diego, CA, USA).
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Competing interests: Rice University owns intellectual property on the use of electromagnetic (light) activation of MM for the killing of cells. This intellectual property has been licensed to a company in which JMT is a stockholder, although he is not an officer or director of that company. CAO is currently an employee in that company. Conflicts of interest are mitigated through regular disclosure to the Rice University Office of Sponsored Projects and Research Compliance. All other authors declare they have no competing interests.

Data and materials availability: Bacterial strains and cell lines are commercially available from ATCC and DSMZ. All the necessary details for the synthesis of MM are provided in the Supplementary Information. Detailed methods and results from computational analysis of MM parameters are provided in the Supplementary Information. Other than the specific datasets and analysis code listed below, all data are available in the main text or the supplementary materials. Raw electron microscopy images and RNAseq data have been deposited in public databases and are available.

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Figures and Tables

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Fig. 1. MM as antibacterials. (A) General structure of an MM. (B) Rotation cycle of an MM. Photoisomerization of the MM (**1**→**2**) generates the metastable conformer, **2**. Following the thermal helix inversion step (**2**→**3**), during which the methyl group moves from the *pseudo* equatorial to *pseudo* axial position and the naphthalene moiety in the rotor moves behind the stator, a second stable conformer, **3**, is generated. A subsequent photoisomerization step (**3**→**4**) and corresponding thermal helix inversion (**4**→**1**) generates the full 360-degree rotation cycle. (C) Schematic representation of an MM drilling through the cell membrane as would occur following light activation. (D) Overview of the workflow used in this study and the different MM examined at each step. (E) MIC value of different MM in *E. coli* BW25113. Arrows next to the bars denote that the MIC value was higher than the maximal concentration (40 μ M) tested. Bars represent the results from at least 3 biological replicas. (F) Chemical structure of the antibacterial MM identified in this study. (G) Schematic representation of the different positioning of MM **1** and MM **2** in the bacterial membrane based on results from MD simulations.

Fig. 2. MM are fast-acting, broad-spectrum antibacterials. (A) Time-dependent reduction in the abundance of different exponentially-growing bacterial strains in the presence of 1% DMSO or 2x MIC of each MM and 146 mW cm^{-2} of 405 nm light, or 2x and 4x the MIC of conventional antibiotics. The dashed line denotes the limit of detection of the method. Results are the mean of at least 3 biological replicas \pm standard error of the mean. (B) MIC value of MM **1**, MM **5**, MM **6** in different Gram-negative and Gram-positive strains, including MRSA. Bars represent the results from at least 3 biological replicas. Unless otherwise noted, results for MM and DMSO are always reported in the presence of light.

1095 **Fig. 3. MM eliminate persisters and biofilms without detectable resistance.** (A) Time-
1096 dependent reduction in the abundance of persister cells of different bacterial strains in the
1097 presence of 1% DMSO or 1x MIC of each MM and 405 nm light at 146 mW cm⁻², or 2x
1098 and 4x the MIC of conventional antibiotics. The dashed line denotes the limit of detection
1099 of the method. Reduction in (B) total bacterial cell number assessed using acridine orange,
1100 (C) metabolically active cells assessed from ATP levels, (D) total protein assessed using
1101 FITC fluorescence, and (E) total biomass assessed using crystal violet in established
1102 biofilms of *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*, following irradiation (146 mW cm⁻² of 405 nm
1103 light) for different time periods in the presence of 1% DMSO or 2x MIC of MM, or in the
1104 presence of 2x MIC of conventional antibiotics. Results are shown as the mean of at least 3
1105 biological replicas ± standard error of the mean. (F) MIC fold change relative to the original
1106 MIC following repeated exposure to MM, and control antibiotics. Results are shown as the
1107 average of at least 3 biological replicas. Unless otherwise noted, results for MM and DMSO
1108 are always reported in the presence of light.

1110 **Fig. 4. MM- and DMSO-treated cells display distinct transcriptomic profiles.** (A)
1111 RNAseq workflow. (B) Venn diagram of the transcriptomic profiles of MM and DMSO-
1112 treated samples. (C) Heat map representation of z-scores for gene transcripts displaying an
1113 adjusted p-value < 0.01 and the highest fold change in abundance in MM and DMSO-treated
1114 samples. (D) Volcano plot of statistically significant (p < 0.05) differentially expressed
1115 genes identified from the RNASeq libraries. Results are the average of 3 biological replicas.

1117 **Fig. 5. Mechanisms of action of visible light-activated MM.** (A) Uptake of *N*-phenyl-1-
1118 naphthylamine (NPN) by the *E. coli* outer membrane following treatment with 1% DMSO
1119 or different concentrations of MM. (B) Time progression of PI fluorescence following
1120 treatment of *E. coli* with different concentrations of MM or 1% DMSO. (C) Extracellular
1121 ATP levels following treatment of *E. coli* with 1% DMSO or different concentrations of
1122 MM. (D) Fluorescence of the membrane potential probe DiSC₃(5) following treatment of
1123 *E. coli* with 1% DMSO or different concentrations of MM. All results are shown as the
1124 mean of at least 3 biological replicas ± standard error of the mean. (E) TEM images of *E.*
1125 *coli* treated with 1% DMSO or 0.5x MIC of MM. (F) SEM images of *E. coli* treated with
1126 1% DMSO or 0.5x MIC of MM. Unless otherwise noted, results for MM and DMSO are
1127 always reported in the presence of light.

1129 **Fig. 6. MM sensitize bacteria to conventional antibiotics.** (A) MIC values of different
1130 antibiotics in *E. coli* with or without pre-treatment with light-activated MM. (B) FIC index
1131 for the interaction between MM and different antibiotics in *E. coli*. (C) Workflow used to
1132 investigate the ability of MM to potentiate antibiotic activity. (D) Reduction in cell numbers
1133 following treatment of *E. coli* with 1% DMSO, 0.5x MIC of different MM, 4x MIC of
1134 different antibiotics alone or in combination, or upon challenging 0.5x MIC MM-treated
1135 cells with 4x MIC of antibiotics. (E) Time-dependent increase in tetracycline fluorescence
1136 in *E. coli* following pre-treatment of cells with 1% DMSO or MM. (F) Representative
1137 checkerboards depicting the interaction between visible light-activated MM and
1138 vancomycin in *P. aeruginosa*. A slow MM (ARV-3-202) was used as a control. Results are
1139 shown as a heatmap with the white color denoting no growth (0 %) and the blue color
1140 denoting growth. Growth was assessed as OD₆₀₀. (G) Time-kill curves of *P. aeruginosa*
1141 treated with 0.25x MIC of the different visible light-activated MM and subsequently
1142 challenged with vancomycin. Vancomycin-only and MM-only treated samples, as well as
1143 DMSO controls, were also examined. All experiments were conducted at least in triplicate.
1144 Where appropriate, results are shown as the mean of at least 3 biological replicas ± standard

1145 error of the mean. Unless otherwise noted, results for MM and DMSO are always reported
1146 in the presence of light.

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1148 **Fig. 7. MM mitigate mortality *in vivo*.** (A) Workflow used to assess the *in vivo*
1149 antibacterial effects of MM. (B) Percent survival of *G. mellonella* infected with *A.*
1150 *baumannii* or *S. aureus* and treated with 1x MIC of different MM, 1% DMSO in the
1151 presence or absence of 405 nm light, or the antibiotics polymyxin or tobramycin. Data
1152 represent the pooled results from 3 independent biological replicas, each containing 16
1153 individuals. Unless otherwise noted, results for MM and DMSO are always reported in the
1154 presence of light.
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1156 Fig. 1A
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1160 Fig. 1B
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1175 Fig. 1E
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E. coli BW25113

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Fig. 1F

MM 1 (DL-4-654)

MW: 462.6550

3 MHz

MM 2 (DL-4-726)

MW: 462.6550

3 MHz

MM 3 (DL-4-751)

MW: 476.6820

3 MHz

MM 4 (DL-4-800)

MW: 827.8608

3 MHz

MM 5 (DL-5-877)

MW: 462.6550

3 MHz

MM 6 (DL-5-878)

MW: 434.6010

3 MHz

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Fig. 2A

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Fig. 2B

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Fig. 3A

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Fig. 3E

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Fig. 4A

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Fig. 4B

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1264 Fig. 5A

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Fig. 5D

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Fig. 5E

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Fig. 5F

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Fig. 6A

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Fig. 6B

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Fig. 6F

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Fig. 6G

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